

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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SCHOOL NURSES AND CARE COORDINATION FOR CHILDREN WITH
COMPLEX NEEDS: AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2014

ABSTRACT

Health care for students with chronic needs can be complex and specialized resulting in fragmentation, duplication, and inefficiencies. Students who miss school due to chronic conditions lose valuable educational exposure that contributes to academic success. As health-related disabilities increase in prevalence so does the need for the coordination of care within the school and between the school and service providing agencies. This integrative literature review provides a synthesis of published evidence identifying and describing the core concepts associated with the role of school nurses in providing care coordination to students with complex needs. Six core essentials of nurse provided care coordination were identified: collaboration, communication, care planning and the nursing process, coordination, clinical expertise, and reinforcing components. Recommendations for improving care coordination were elucidated in the review. Analysis of the literature can help assure application of best practice methods for the coordination of care for students in the school setting.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I could never have completed this program and this project without the support, love, and assistance of my “pit crew,” Eddie, Livia and Adeline. Eddie, you make my life easier in every way, I hope I do the same for you. I can’t tell you how much I love and admire you; I am so glad we have each other. Livia you are wonderful, empathetic, funny, creative, friendly, and smart. Adeline you are marvelous, silly, self-assured, friendly, and also super smart. The sacrifices were great and I appreciate you all. We have the best family, I am so lucky!

A special thanks to Dr. Weismuller, my project chair who has shown great patience, wisdom, guidance, and respect throughout this journey. To my committee members Dr. Dana Rutledge and Dr. Cindy Greenberg, thank you for your valuable expertise, insights, and comments on my project and throughout the program. I have the best committee!

I am fortunate to have many friends and colleagues who have helped me believe in myself and continued to push me onward throughout this process. Thanks especially to Tina Graves, Jennifer Lasley (and the OSD nurses), Karen Sher, and Deborah Rannalli who were always there to keep me inspired.

Finally, to my mother, Lynn Taylor, my father, the late Donald McClanahan (1941 – 1990), and my great grandmother, Betty Porges who helped me build a solid foundation from which to pursue this lifelong dream.

PROCESSES PROPOSED AND UNDERTAKEN

Introduction

Many factors, including health, can impact a child's ability to learn and succeed academically. Missing school days or in-class time due to illness or chronic condition causes children to lose important instructional exposure. There are approximately 11 million children in the United States, 15% of all US children, under the age of 18 who have chronic conditions or who could be categorized as children and youth with special health care needs (CYSHCN) (Bloom, Cohen, & Freeman, 2012; Center for Child and Adolescent Health, 2012; McPherson, Arango, & Fox, 1998; United States Department of Health and Human Services [USDHHS], 2012). CYSHCN have long-term medical, behavioral, emotional, cognitive, or developmental conditions that require health and related services, beyond what is required by typical children, these include specialized therapies, education aids, or prescription medications (Bloom et al., 2012; McPherson et al., 1998). Families of CYSHCN face the complex maze of the United States health care system, and related support systems, as they take steps to get needed services. Complex care that requires the involvement of primary care providers, multiple specialties, support and therapy providers, and community and educational services, can be fragmented, with gaps and duplications in care that impact quality and increase overall cost (Fuchs, 2009; Nolan, Orlando, & Liptak, 2007).

Historically, children with chronic health conditions and disabilities were confined to therapeutic institutional settings or their homes. Their education was either provided for by expensive private education or disregarded (Dang, 2010; Winzer, 1993). Upon the enactment of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), originally

ratified in 1975 and amended in 2004, children were provided the opportunity to receive to a free and appropriate education in the least restrictive environment no matter the severity of their disabilities (United States Department of Education [USDE], 2004). Today children with a multitude of disabilities, chronic illnesses, and complex health needs are routinely seen in general education as well as special education programs. CYSHCN attend school and succeed in part due to the essential support services provided by school nurses. Through the development of health care plans, school nurses are responsible to and accountable for planning, implementation, provision, and monitoring of the ongoing health care needs for students with chronic health conditions (National Association of School Nurses [NASN], 2012, Selekman, 2013).

School nursing is a dynamic and complex specialty that includes not only direct care activities but also health screening, referral, and follow up, case and care management, communicable disease control, health promotion, and leadership in developing sound health and safety policies (NASN, 2011). Numerous studies have documented the positive impact of school nursing services on decreased absenteeism, reduced time spent outside of the classroom, and improved management of chronic health conditions (Allen, 2003; Pennington & Delaney, 2008; Weismuller, Grasska, Alexander, White, & Kramer, 2007; Wyman, 2005). The increasingly complex and persistent health needs of children in schools contribute to the expansion of the role of school nurses as case managers.

Management and coordination of care and services for children with chronic health conditions and special health care needs is an ongoing challenge for service and health providers (Toomey, Chien, Elliott, Ratner, & Schuster, 2013). Coordination of

care is one of the national health care quality improvement priorities identified by the Institute of Medicine (2001) in *Crossing the Quality Chasm: A New Health System for the 21st Century*. The Affordable Care Act (ACA) health care reform law has established coordinated care as an essential aspect in improving the quality of the US health care system (Fuchs, 2009; Orszag & Emanuel, 2010; USDHHS, 2002; USDHHS, 2010). Section 2717 of the ACA, “Ensuring the Quality of Care,” requires the establishment of “reimbursement structure that improve health outcomes through the implementation of activities such as quality reporting, effective case management, care coordination, chronic disease management” (USDHHS, 2010, p. 30). Additionally, the ACA establishes a market-based incentive program for those providing effective case management and care coordination and specifically includes “nurse care coordinator” as part of the team of health professionals who will assure that quality care (Looman et al., 2013; USDHHS, 2010).

One method of coping with fragmentation, duplication, and gaps in service is to provide a system of culturally competent and family-centered care coordination and case management (Nolan et al., 2007). The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) defines care coordination as a method of linking children with special health care needs, and their families, to services and resources in an organized way, providing optimal health care and maximizing their potential for well-being (AAP, 2005). Similarly, case management is defined as a method of facilitating the coordination of services via a process of assessment, planning, communication, and collaboration to advocate for options to achieve high quality, cost effective, and efficient outcomes (Case Management Society of America [CMSA], 2010).

Comprehensive case management by school nurses takes place daily, both formally and informally, in many school districts. School nurses are concerned not only with the achievement of health related outcomes but also academic outcomes that contribute to current and future well-being. Because school nurses are so deeply involved in the care of students with chronic conditions, they are often the only health care providers aware of all the services and agencies involved with these student and their families (Selekman, 2013). With the current changes in national health care and the focus on preventive, efficient, and effective quality care, school nurses are in a key position to provide comprehensive case management and coordination of services.

Supporting Framework

The primary model guiding this project is the Case Management Body of Knowledge (CMBOK)[®], introduced by the Commission for Case Manager Certification (CCMC) in 2011. The CMBOK provides a comprehensive organized framework as a tool for better understanding of the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to be considered a competent case manager able to provide effective care (CCMC, 2011).

The CMBOK is made up of seven case management knowledge domains including: case management concepts, principles of practice, health care management and delivery, healthcare reimbursement, psychosocial aspects of care, rehabilitation, and professional development advancement. All of the seven knowledge domains, which can be applied in any practice setting, are intertwined and connected to the nine-step case management process (CCMC, 2011). The knowledge domains comprise the scope of case management work and subdomains further clarify each domain.

The nine process phases for providing case management services and interventions are screening, assessing, stratifying risk, planning, implementing care coordination, following-up, transitioning, communicating post-transition, and evaluating. The case management process is ongoing and iterative in order to achieve desired outcomes (CCMC, 2011). Together the knowledge domains and the case management process reinforce the value of case management.

The case management philosophy and guiding principles and the Standards of Practice for Case Management maintain that case management is a collaborative and interdisciplinary specialty that takes place in various practice settings along the health and human services continuum (Case Management Society of America [CMSA], 2010; CCMC, 2011). Because case management occurs in a variety of settings the nine-step case management process is adapted to individual settings. As a cross-disciplinary, interdependent, adjustable specialty practice, rather than a singular professional specialty occurring in a hospital or clinic, case management principles and knowledge domains in other specialty areas such as school nursing can be explored.

Problem Statement

Health care provided for students with chronic health needs and multiple disabilities can be highly specialized, and is sometimes fragmented, ineffective, and associated with high costs and inefficiency. Students with complex health care needs attend public schools and often require school nurse support. Students who miss school due to a chronic health condition lose out of valuable educational exposure that contributes to their overall academic success. As health-related disabilities increase in prevalence so does the need for the coordination of care and services both within the

school and between the school and service providing agencies in the community. Both the AAP (2008) and NASN (2011) write that a key role of school nurses is to act as case managers and liaisons, and to foster adequate communication and collaboration between school staff, families, community and the health care system to ensure consistent and coordinated care. Despite the policy statement description and promotion of school nurses as case managers, there is a lack of understanding about the role of school nurses in providing case management services.

Purpose of the Project

In order to assure application of best practice methods for the care of students in the school setting and the health care system at large, it is important to have a better understanding of the role of school nurses in providing comprehensive case management and care coordination. The purpose of this project was to identify and clarify the expanded role of school nurses as case managers.

Research Questions, Goals and Objectives

The goals of this project were as follows:

- 1) To provide a systematic integrative review of the research related to the provision of case management services for children with chronic health conditions and their families, and to explore the feasibility and advantages of the provision of case management services by school nurses.
- 2) To provide evidence-based recommendations to inform policy and practice.
- 3) To recommend priorities for future research.

Methods

Study Design

An integrative review of the literature was conducted related to the provision of case management and case coordination services provided to children with chronic health conditions, and their families. Institutional review board approval was not required for this type of research because it does not involve the use of human subjects and did not include review of medical records.

The purpose of an integrative review is to critique and synthesize a body of research in order to offer better understanding and draw conclusions about a phenomenon or problem (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005). Integrative reviews of the literature can provide a new framework and ways of thinking about a topic, method of treatment, or area of concern. A great advantage of using the integrative review approach is the practice of data combination across studies of different types, methods, and designs, including theoretical as well as empirical (Whittemore, 2005; Whittemore & Knafl). An integrative review requires the same high standards of rigor in methods expected of a well-designed primary research study (Ganong, 1987; Cooper, 1998, Whittemore, 2005; Whittemore & Knafl, 2005).

In order to maintain rigor in the integrative review process, the framework for conducting an integrative review suggested by Cooper (1998), Whittemore and Knafl (2005), and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was used for this project. Whittemore and Knafl (2005) offer overall instruction on the process of conducting an integrative review, focusing on the need for carefully and properly conducting the data analysis, synthesis, and conclusion drawing

stages of process. The PRISMA statement, developed to help assure rigor and standardization in reporting findings for systematic reviews and meta-analyses, also guided this review project. The PRISMA flow diagram aids in identifying usable studies during the literature search process and checklist was developed to assure that each usable document is thoroughly and properly examined (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, Altman, & the PRISMA Group, 2009). Cooper (1998) distinguishes the following stages of the integrative review process: (a) formulating a problem statement; (b) collecting data via a literature search; (c) evaluating the data by assessing the quality of the studies; (d) analyzing and interpreting the data; and (e) presenting the results. Cooper stresses that each stage has the same function as those used in the process of conducting classic primary research. The focus of the research in this study was the identification of patterns, themes, subgroups, and relationships to identify the evidence base for clarifying the role of the school nurse in providing case management and care coordination services.

Problem Formulation

The initial stage of an integrative review is problem identification, where the variables of interest and the purpose of the review are identified (Cooper, 1998). The problem to be addressed in this review was the lack of understanding of the school nurse role in providing case management and care coordination services for children with chronic health conditions. The purpose of the integrative review was to examine the provision of case management and care coordination services and explore the feasibility and advantages of the provision of case management services by school nurses. Having a well-specified purpose and variable of interest helped in differentiating between relevant

and unrelated information and provide focus and limits for the process (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005).

Too narrowly defining variables so that the quality of the findings is low or impaired because other operational definitions are not considered can be a threat to validity (Cooper, 1998). Cooper states that unlike primary research, synthesis research can begin with only loose conceptual definitions, and a few operations for measurement, and then allow operations to grow more precise as knowledge of the literature increases. Cooper also warns against definitions that are too broad as this can cause reviewers to overlook details and incorrectly interpret results.

Data Collection

The literature search stage of the review process is critical for properly analyzing and describing the phenomena in question. If data is collected from a search that is incomplete or inadequate in scope, is not exhaustive, or lacks adherence to the inclusion or exclusion criteria there can be bias and the drawing of flawed conclusions (Cooper, 1998; Whittemore, 2005). Difficulty in obtaining all relevant research studies is noted by Whittemore and Knafl (2005) who suggest that synthesis researchers use at least two research strategies to assure the search is exhaustive. In selecting the sample to research the generalizability and conclusions are enhanced with greater representativeness of the population being examined (Ganong, 1987). A table of evidence, to organize data in a clear and concise format and to enhance collection of consistent information from all sources, will be utilized.

The target populations for this synthesis research project were nurses providing case management or case coordination, or both, in the schools and in the community, to

children with special health care needs, and their families. Inclusion of nurses providing case management outside of the school setting allowed the researcher to examine and allow for generalizations to nurses within the school setting (Cooper, 1998). Ganong (1987) suggests that inclusion criteria be more tentative and that substantive or methodological changes be made if suggested by the findings in the literature.

A professional librarian was consulted prior to beginning the search to assure an adequate literature search. A comprehensive computer-assisted search was conducted of the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), MEDLINE, PubMed, Cochrane, and PsycINFO, to identify relevant articles about nurses providing case management and case coordination to children with special health care needs. As suggested by Whitemore and Knafl (2005) studies including different methodologies were included. Articles published between 1990 and 2013 were included for primary review. This time frame was selected because it allowed for inclusion of research performed after both the 1975 law establishing the right of student with health conditions to attend school and the establishment of the “prospective payment system” and diagnostic related groups (DRG) established in 1983 (Kulesher, 2006).

Articles pertaining to nurses providing case management in a hospital setting were excluded, as in-patient and discharge planning forms of case management are not pertinent. Because the health care system in the United States is unique and relevant in context to the current changes in the system only articles written in English and from the United States were included. Articles were also obtained from a historical search, using reference lists and bibliographies. Unpublished dissertations were included. Moyer, Schneider, Knapp-Oliver, and Sohl (2010), in their study examining the quality of

unpublished dissertations, found that because dissertations are typically easy to access, free from some forms of bias, and tend to have thorough reporting of findings, they merit inclusion in reviews.

Data Evaluation

A critical judgment about the quality of the data contained within selected articles occurred during the data evaluation phase. Whether or not a study was included in the analysis was decided as each study was evaluated. Because this integrative review included diverse primary sources with differing methodology, evaluating quality was difficult. Whittemore and Knafl (2005) write that no gold standard for evaluating and interpreting quality for this situation currently exists and suggest that evaluation of quality in an integrative review is variable depending on the frame of sampling.

Utilization of the PRISMA checklist, as well as guidelines for critiquing qualitative and quantitative research provided by Polit and Beck (2012), was used to assure quality in studies of different design. Both guidelines take into consideration review of sample, study protocol, measurement, attrition, threats to validity, intervention, statistical analysis, and discussion. In order to ensure accuracy a second reviewer was used to confirm interrater agreement, depending on the complexity of the study or need for analysis. Cooper (1998) cautions that the tendency to either positively evaluate research congruent with the researcher's hypothesis, or negatively evaluate those in contradiction of that hypothesis, are threats to validity during this phase.

Data Analysis

The data analysis phase includes ordering, coding, categorizing, thoroughly analyzing, impartially interpreting, and then summarizing the data found in the articles

selected for inclusion. Once completed, a unified and integrated conclusion about the research problem was formulated (Cooper, 1998; Whitemore & Knafl, 2005). Because this study was not a meta-analysis of randomized control trials and included results from both qualitative and quantitative studies, a qualitative analysis was performed. Use of a table that includes associations among codes, concepts, themes, and ideas was developed in this phase of the review. Whitemore and Knafl, concerned with the possibility of error in the analysis phase of the integrative review due to the lack of formal processes, suggest utilization of a systematic analytic method. An approach to data analysis that included a constant comparison method consisting of data reduction, data display, and data comparison, in addition to conclusion drawing and verification, was used in this review (Whitemore & Knafl, 2005).

Data reduction. The primary sources included in this integrative review were divided into subgroups based on classification such as type of evidence, setting, sample, or other conceptual classification (Whitemore & Knafl, 2005). If type of evidence classification is used, Whitemore and Knafl suggest sequential analysis beginning with all qualitative and descriptive studies, followed by correlational or comparative design studies, and lastly intervention or experimental design studies. Extraction and coding of data was performed in order to focus and organize the information into a useable framework. Whitemore and Knafl suggest data from each subgroup be extracted and compiled onto a spreadsheet so that each source is collected along with similar data from within each subgroup classification. This was done.

Data display. The assembly and display of data from multiple sources, around a variable or subgroup, was the next step. The display can take on any form, simple or

complex, with the ultimate purpose being ease in ability to compare patterns and relationships across primary sources as the process of interpretation begins. Whitemore and Knafl (2005) suggest that different types of displays will likely be necessary for each subgroup classification in the review. Tables of evidence were used to display data from studies in school and data from studies in other pediatric healthcare settings.

Data comparison. This stage involved repetitively examining data to identify patterns, themes, and relationships and then displaying them in a conceptual map (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005). On the map, similar variables were grouped so that relationships between variables and themes are depicted. Whitemore and Knafl offer strategies for data comparison, all of which are concerned with enhancing data comparison and interpretation that help identify accurate and meaningful patterns and themes. Strategies suggested by Whitemore and Knafl were examined individually and chosen for use based on best fit with the needs of the data comparison for this review.

Conclusion drawing and verification. During the final phase of data analysis, commonalities and differences are identified and a set of generalizations from each subgroup began to emerge. Any conclusions of conceptual models that emerge were revised and verified to include as much data as possible (Whitemore & Knafl, 2005). Dealing with conflicting evidence is a concern during this phase due to the chance of there being equally compelling positive and negative findings about a particular item. Cooper (1998) suggests comparing the frequency of findings, either positive or negative, to resolve this problem. Compelling but conflicting findings point to the need for additional research in that area. Finally, summarizing a comprehensive representation of the topic from the synthesis of important elements and conclusions completed the review

process. As suggested by Whitemore and Knafl, records were kept during the entire process to document the transparent and honest process of qualitative analytic decision-making.

Presentation

Properly reporting both the specific detailed methods of the review, in addition to the findings, is key to maintaining the rigor of the process. Omission of important details about how the review was conducted weakens the impact of findings as validity would be in question and the study could be rendered not replicable (Cooper, 1998; Whitemore & Knafl, 2005). Results from primary studies were reported in narrative format so that readers may assess the basis of the conclusions drawn. Tables were also used so that key evidence, such as sample sizes, type of design, or setting, is easily discernible. Allowing the reader examination of this data offers proof that the review conclusions did not exceed the evidence (Whitemore, 2005; Whitemore & Knafl, 2005). The presentation phase in this project included summary and descriptive information of the literature reviewed and offered a critique of methods and applicability to practice.

Integrative reviews help researchers evaluate the strength of scientific evidence, identify gaps in research and need for further research, help build bridges, and identify central issues within and between areas of research. Integrative reviews, because they include diverse data from studies with differing methods, offer comprehensive understanding of problems relevant to the healthcare system. However, combining dissimilar data is complex and challenging and fraught with error. Utilization of the systematic processes suggested by Cooper (1998), Whitemore and Knafl (2005), and the

PRISMA format (2009) guided this project in order to maintain rigor and decrease bias and inaccuracy.

EVALUATION METHODS

This project was continuously evaluated both by the author, faculty advisor, and committee members, as it evolved to assure that the product maintained the rigor described in the methods and met the requirements of the Doctor of Nursing Practice program. Prior to journal submission for publication, content specialists will be asked to review the final manuscript to assure validity of findings.

RESULTS

The product of this integrative review was the creation of a manuscript submitted to the Journal of School Nursing, found in Appendix A. Guidelines for manuscript submission to the Journal of School Nursing is found in Appendix B. This presentation was selected for podium presentation at the National Association for School Nurses annual conference on Sunday, June 29, 2014 in San Antonio, Texas. The California State University (CSU) Chancellor's Office has accepted this presentation in poster format for the Showcase of Excellence in CSU Nursing Education and Scholarly Projects and Research on May 21, 2014 in Long Beach, CA. Finally, this project has been submitted for podium presentation at the 2014 American School Health Association School Health Conference in Portland, Oregon, October 8 – 11, 2014.

DISCUSSION

The conclusions of this integrative review demonstrate that when performing case management and care coordination, school nurses provide services by adhering to the six core essentials of collaboration, communication, care planning and the nursing process, coordination, clinical expertise, and additional critical components, such as cultural competency and a focus on prevention, among others. Having a better understanding and verifying the components of case management for school nurses is important to support the work occurring in schools across the country. This review reconfirms the need for school nurses to develop mechanisms for documentation of assessments, interventions, and outcomes of case management activities. Direction for future study into the application of case management and care coordination in the school setting by establishing baseline data, developing outcome measures, and distinguishing nurse-sensitive indicators are recommended. Unfortunately, this review again confirms the systematic barriers to school nurse practice, including the competing priorities of the educational system, fiscal challenges, staffing shortages, and a general misunderstanding of the role of the school nurse.

As a school nurse currently in practice, this review has helped me to think more deeply about both how I provide services and how I document those services. I am inspired to take the next step to begin to investigate categories and classifications for documentation of activities and outcomes.

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APPENDIX A

MANUSCRIPT SUBMITTED *TO THE JOURNAL OF SCHOOL NURSING*

School Nurses and Care Coordination for Children with Complex Needs:

An Integrative Review

Abstract

Health care for students with chronic needs can be complex and specialized resulting in fragmentation, duplication, and inefficiencies. Students who miss school due to chronic conditions lose valuable educational exposure that contributes to academic success. As health-related disabilities increase in prevalence so does the need for the coordination of care within the school and between the school and service providing agencies. This integrative literature review provides a synthesis of published evidence identifying and describing the core concepts associated with the role of school nurses in providing care coordination to students with complex needs. Six core essentials of nurse provided care coordination were identified: collaboration, communication, care planning and the nursing process, coordination, clinical expertise, and reinforcing components. Recommendations for improving care coordination were elucidated in the review. Analysis of the literature can help assure application of best practice methods for the coordination of care for students in the school setting.

Introduction

Children with special health care needs have long-term medical, behavioral, emotional, cognitive, or developmental conditions that can impact learning. They may

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require health and related services, such as specialized therapies, education aids, or prescription medications, beyond what is required by typical children (Bloom, Cohen, & Freeman, 2012; McPherson, Arango, & Fox, 1998). Of the approximately 11 million children under the age of 18 in the United States, 15% have chronic conditions or could be categorized as having special health care needs (Bloom et al., 2012; Center for Child and Adolescent Health, 2012; McPherson et al., 1998; United States Department of Health and Human Services [USDHHS], 2012). Their cost of health care, because of the increased usage of services, is many times higher than their counterparts without disabilities (Newacheck, Inkelas, & Kim, 2004). These families face a complex maze of health care and related support systems as they attempt to acquire needed services. With the potential to involve primary care providers, multiple specialties, support and therapy providers, and community, mental health, and educational services, care delivery can be fragmented, with gaps and duplications in care that impact quality and increase overall cost (Fuchs, 2009; Nolan, Orlando, & Liptak, 2007).

Historically, children with chronic health conditions and disabilities were confined to therapeutic institutional settings or their homes, and their academic needs were either provided by private education, or completely omitted (Dang, 2010; Winzer, 1993). Upon the enactment of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), ratified in 1975 and amended in 2004, these children were entitled to receive a free and appropriate education in the least restrictive environment no matter the severity of their disability (United States Department of Education [USDE], 2004). Today, children with

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disabilities, chronic conditions and complex health needs are routinely seen in general education as well as in special education settings.

Children with special health care needs attend school and succeed due in part to the essential support services provided by school nurses, who are accountable for their ongoing health care needs (National Association of School Nurses [NASN], 2012; Selekman, 2013). School nurses provide direct care nursing activities as well as health screening, referrals, follow-up, case management, communicable disease control, health promotion, and leadership in developing sound health and safety policies and procedures (NASN, 2011). They positively impact student outcomes such as decreased absenteeism, reduced time spent away from the classroom, and improved management of health conditions (Allen, 2003; Engelke, Guttu, Warren, & Swanson, 2008; Levy, Heffner, Stewart, & Beeman, 2006; Moricca, Grasska, Marthaler, Morphew, Weismuller, & Galant, 2012; Pennington & Delaney, 2008; Weismuller, Grasska, Alexander, White, & Kramer, 2007; Wyman, 2005). School nurses provide the highly complex coordinated care and oversight for the increasingly complex and persistent health needs of children in educational settings.

Coordinated Care

Nationally, management and coordination of care and services for children with chronic health conditions and special health care needs is an ongoing challenge for service and health providers (Toomey, Chien, Elliott, Ratner, & Schuster, 2013).

Coordination of care is a health care quality improvement priority (Institute of Medicine,

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2001). The Affordable Care Act (ACA) health care reform law has further established coordinated care as an essential aspect in improving U.S. health care quality (Fuchs, 2009; Orszag & Emanuel, 2010; USDHHS, 2010). Section 2717 of the ACA, “Ensuring the Quality of Care,” requires the establishment of a “reimbursement structure that improves health outcomes through the implementation of activities such as quality reporting, effective case management, care coordination, chronic disease management” (USDHHS, 2010, p. 30). Additionally, the ACA establishes market-based incentives for providing effective case management and care coordination, specifically including “nurse care coordinator” as part of the team of health professionals (Looman, Presler, Erickson, Garwick, Cady, Kelly, & Finkelstein, 2013; USDHHS, 2010).

Healthcare providers, researchers, professional organizations, and policy makers agree that care coordination is a key element to improving processes and outcomes, especially for medically complex and socially underserved populations (American Academy of Pediatrics [AAP], 1999; USDHHS, 2010; Ziring et al., 1999). Optimal care coordination includes proactive methods of coping with fragmentation, duplication, high cost, and gaps in service, which provides culturally competent and family-centered care (Nolan et al., 2007).

Definitions

Care coordination and case management have slightly different definitions, depending on the setting and system of care using the term. However, for the purposes of

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this integrative review, “care coordination” and “case management” are used interchangeably to mean the following:

a deliberate organization of patient care activities between two or more participants (including the patient) involved in a patient’s care to facilitate the appropriate delivery of health care services. Organizing care involves the marshaling of personnel and other resources needed to carry out all required patient care activities, and is often managed by the exchange of information among participants responsible for different aspects of care. (McDonald et al., 2010, p. 4)

Case Management and School Nurses

Case management has long been a core professional standard and competency for all nursing practice specialty areas and comprises Standard 5A of the *Scope and Standards of Practice* for school nursing (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2011; ANA, 2012; Selekman, 2013). Comprehensive case management provided by school nurses, both formally and informally, takes place daily in many school districts across the country. The activities and priorities of such case management vary broadly depending on availability of services. School nurses demonstrate their roles as case managers by interacting and communicating with families of children with special health care needs, school staff, health care providers, and community agencies. Creating, updating, and implementing care plans, and working comprehensively to create an environment where students will achieve academic success and maintain optimal health is fundamental.

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School nurses work across multiple systems including education, healthcare, public health, insurance, and community agencies to assure that student needs are met.

School nurses interact regularly with children with special health care needs when providing direct care (e.g., treatments, education, follow-up), and indirectly when doing general care planning, or supervising support staff providing care. They are concerned not only with the achievement of health-related outcomes, but also with developmental and academic outcomes that contribute to current and future wellbeing. School nurses are deeply immersed in all aspects of the care of students with chronic conditions and are often the only health care providers aware of all services and agencies involved with these students and family members (Selekman, 2013). With recent national health care changes and the imperative for preventive, efficient, and effective quality care, school nurses are strategically positioned to provide comprehensive case management and coordination of services.

Purpose

In order to assure application of best practice methods for the care of students in the educational setting and the health care system at large, it is important to fully understand the role of school nurses in providing comprehensive case management. The purpose of this review was to provide a synthesis of published evidence to identify and clarify this expanded role, to provide evidence-based recommendations to inform policy and practice, and to recommend priorities for future research. This review was

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completed to answer the question, what are the core concepts associated with the role of school nurses in providing case management and care coordination?

Methods

An integrative review of the literature was conducted related to the provision of case management and care coordination services provided to children with chronic health conditions, and their families. This review used strategies described by Cooper (1998), Whittemore and Knafl (2005), and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, Altman, & the PRISMA Group, 2009). The purpose of an integrative review is to locate, synthesize, and critique a body of research in order to offer better understanding of, and draw conclusions about, a phenomenon or problem (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005). Critical analysis of the literature includes an examination of the historical context or origin of a topic or issue, including main concepts, relationships and interactions of those concepts (Torraco, 2005).

Search Strategies

Several key words were used to search for articles on case management and care coordination for children with special health care needs. Combinations of search terms including “case management,” “care coordination,” “service coordination,” “pediatrics,” “children,” “school nurse,” and “special health care needs” were used to search four computerized databases: Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, PsychInfo, and Academic Search Premier. Search methods were

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validated by a California State University librarian. The inclusion and exclusion criteria shown in Table 1 were applied.

Inclusion criteria included articles focused on nurses providing case management or care coordination to children with special health care needs, and their families in schools, the community, ambulatory care facilities, and in-patient facilities. Because the health care system in the United States is unique and relevant in context to the current changes in the system, only articles written in English and focusing on settings in the United States were included. Articles published between 1990 and 2013 were included for primary review. This time frame was selected because it allowed for inclusion of research performed after both the 1975 law establishing the right of students with health conditions to attend school and the establishment of the “prospective payment system” and diagnostic related groups (DRG) established in 1983 (Kulesher, 2006). Because of potential changes made during establishment of stable structure of DRG payment system, articles written between 1984 and 1990 were excluded. Articles were also obtained from reference lists and bibliographies. Unpublished dissertations were included. Moyer, Schneider, Knapp-Oliver, and Sohl (2010), in their study examining the quality of unpublished dissertations, found that because dissertations are typically easy to access, free from some forms of bias, and tend to have thorough reporting of findings, they merit inclusions in reviews. The retrieved literature was reviewed and examined for evidence related to the case management services provided by nurses for pediatric patients with special health care needs.

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Quality Evaluation of Evidence Sources

A critical judgment about the quality and validity of the data contained within selected articles occurs during the data evaluation phase. Inclusion of articles was decided, as each was read and content evaluated by the two primary authors. Because this integrative review includes diverse sources with differing methodology and objectives, the complexity of evaluating quality was more difficult. No gold standard for evaluating and interpreting quality exists, resulting in variable evaluation of quality in an integrative review depending on the sampling frame (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005). Use of the PRISMA checklist, as well as guidelines for critiquing research articles provided by Polit and Beck (2012), aided in assuring quality in the studies of different design. In order to ensure accuracy and control bias, both authors reviewed all articles to increase inter-rater agreement.

Articles selected for the final review were read, and each evidence source was categorized using the Polit and Beck (2012) hierarchy of evidence. This hierarchy provided guidance about types of studies included. In Polit and Beck's (2012) hierarchy, the strongest forms of evidence, categorized as Level I or II, are systematic reviews of randomized control trials and randomized control trials. The weakest types, Levels VI and VII, are the opinions of experts and descriptive and qualitative studies. Most evidence collected for this review was at the lower or weaker end of the hierarchy.

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Data Analysis

As suggested by Whitemore and Knafl (2005), a systematic analytic method was employed to reduce the possibility of error. Articles were categorized and analyzed using a constant comparison method by two reviewers allowing patterns and themes to emerge.

The primary sources included were divided into subgroups based on theme or conceptual classification. Data from each subgroup was extracted and compiled onto a spreadsheet so that each source was categorized with similar data from within each subgroup. Pertinent information collected from the included articles was assembled and presented around variables or subgroups in order to compare patterns and relationships for interpretation. Co-authors repetitively examined these; similar variables were grouped so that relationships between variables and themes could be identified and depicted. Thus, a summary and unified, integrated conclusions about the research problem was formulated (Cooper, 1998; Whitemore & Knafl, 2005).

Search Results

Figure 1 provides an overview of search results using the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009). Twenty-four studies were included. These were largely descriptive studies ($n = 14$) and expert opinion ($n = 9$) along with one randomized control trial. Both authors read the full text of every article, and assessed each against the inclusion criteria to identify those broadly related to nurse-delivered case management and care coordination to pediatric patients and their families. The results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

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Findings

Results are divided into core concepts and elements, case management and care coordination inside or outside of the educational arena, and outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations. While the evidence sources had varied methods and differed greatly in variables measured and discussed, findings reflect a robust consistency in themes and concepts related to the essential elements of case management and care coordination provided by registered nurses in diverse pediatric settings. Six themes regarding the main characteristics associated with nurse provided case management and care coordination were identified: a) collaboration, b) communication, c) care planning and nursing process, d) coordination, e) clinical expertise, f) clinical expertise, and g) reinforcing components.

Collaboration

Collaboration is a main theme running throughout the selected literature and almost every set of authors clearly describes specific collaboration activities (e.g., working with others toward a common goal, while sharing responsibilities, decision making, and rewards; Wells, Johnson, & Salyer, 1998). Building long-term relationships, being an interdisciplinary team leader, emphasizing cross-organizational relationships, and developing partnerships were noted as important actions provided by nurse case managers (Antonelli, McAllister, & Popp, 2009; Barrett, 2000; Engelke et al., 2008).

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Communication

While effective communication is an underlying supposition in considering case management and care coordination as a whole, it was explicitly mentioned and described as a concept to be continuously monitored and improved upon. Phrases such as “facilitate communication” (Gordon, Colby, Bartelt, Jablonski, Krauthoefer, & Havens, 2007; Petitgout, Pelzer, McConkey, & Hanrahan, 2012), “enhance communication” (Kaufman & Blanchon, 1996), and “ensure communication” (Van Roeyen, 2013) were seen more often in the literature from medical settings than in school settings. Several authors detail the concept of having a single nurse as a point-person for contact with families and providers in order to enhance continuity and efficiency of care (Brustrom, Thibadeau, John, Liesmann, & Rose, 2012; Gordon et al., 2007; Looman et al., 2013; Taylor, Lizzi, Marx, Chilkatowsky, Trachetenberg, & Ogle, 2012). Communication was mentioned as a distinct activity or something to be better developed in 2 of 8 school nurse-specific articles (Taras, Wright, Brennan, Campana, & Lofgren, 2004; Van Roeyen, 2013); one of those focused on reporting asthma symptoms to the physician.

Care Planning and Nursing Process

Care planning and nursing process as a general activity or the specific steps of care planning, assessment, planning, intervention, and evaluation, is mentioned in every article in the sample. Case management, as described by Bonaiuto (2007), is the nursing process expanded to include things like population based assessments to identify patients

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or students in need of case management and having a fundamental understanding of, and access to, needed and available resources.

Coordination

Coordination of care encompasses multiple activities for nurses. Brustrom et al. (2012) describe the nurse coordinator of care as being responsible for scheduling appointments with both internal and external providers and organizing clinic day activities for families. When describing Advanced Practice Registered Nurse (APRN)-provided care coordination, Looman and colleagues (2013) note that being a leader in coordinating multidisciplinary care and initiating and managing referrals and monitoring for gaps and overlaps in service are necessary. Coordination of care, or tasks that would be considered coordinating, is mentioned in 3 of 8 school nurse-specific articles and in 12 non-school setting articles.

Clinical Expertise

Clinical expertise is necessary for care coordination. Having responsibility for assisting in the management of disease, being familiar with children's conditions and treatment plans, integrating knowledge of disease process, ensuring correct follow-up, being able to understand, discuss, and apply practice standards and policies, and participating in evidence-based programs and research are all noted as aspects of being a clinical expert (Antonelli, McAllister, & Popp, 2009; Antonelli, Stille, & Antonelli, 2008; Betz & Redcay, 2005; Cady, Kelly, Finkelstein, Looman, & Garwick, 2013; Gordon et al., 2007; Moricca et al., 2012; Van Roeyen, 2013).

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Reinforcing Components

The final theme, reinforcing components, includes those factors described in the literature that enhance or provide a framework or context for case management and care coordination programs. Community-based actions, family- and youth-centered care, providing advocacy, and a focus on prevention are key aspects (Antonelli & Antonelli, 2004; Barrett, 2000; Betz & Redcay, 2005; Lewis, Alford-Winston, Billy-Kornas, McCaustland, & Tachman, 1992; Lindeke, Leonard, Presler, & Garwick, 2002; Petitgout et al., 2012; Presler, 1998). Providing culturally competent, developmentally appropriate care, focusing on early intervention, developing and following standard protocols, using technology, delivering services to promote quality and contain costs, and understanding the importance of improving the health care system so that it is accessible are also concepts linked to case management and care coordination (Antonelli et al., 2009; Betz & Redcay, 2005; Engelke et al., 2008; Kaufman & Blanchon, 1996; Lindeke et al., 2002; Petitgout et al., 2012; Presler, 1998; Van Roeyen, 2013).

Integration of Evidence

While there were differences in elements, approach, and focus between care coordination in the educational and non-educational settings, in general, the core concepts and themes were relatively consistent throughout the sample. Table 1 summarizes the results of the relevant sources ($n = 8$) discussing case management in educational settings. Of the eight school nurse-specific articles, five focused exclusively on the management of students with asthma (Levy et al., 2006; Moricca et al., 2012;

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Taras et al., 2004; Van Roeyen, 2013). One of these included care of children with asthma along with four other chronic illnesses (Engelke et al., 2008). Two of the three remaining articles described implementation of different case management programs (Bonaiuto, 2007; Engelke et al., 2009). One article described a program where nursing students perform various functions of case management as adjuncts to school nurses (Barrett, 2000).

Findings from articles describing care coordination outside of the educational setting ($n = 16$) are summarized in Table 2. A majority of the studies ($n = 14$), were set in primary, secondary, tertiary, hospital, or community-based care areas and not in schools. Each described case management for children with complex medical needs or co-morbidities. Two of the 16 non-education based articles were general descriptions of a pediatric care coordination model or framework (Antonelli et al., 2009; Kaufman & Blanchon, 1996).

The volume of evidence comprised *adequate* quantity despite variation in setting, focus, purpose, variables, and approach to analysis. All authors described best practice elements of case management or care coordination for nursing staff. However, the overall final rating for the body of evidence for this research question was *insufficient*. This does not mean that the evidence reviewed is invalid; rather, it indicates the lack of intervention studies evaluating outcomes of case management in pediatric settings. In fact, outcomes, where measured, varied greatly, including patient satisfaction, early identification and treatment for chronic illnesses, better health outcomes, reduced

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emergency room utilization, or improved school attendance; differences in outcome measurement made comparison across studies difficult (Antonelli & Antonelli, 2004; Antonelli et al., 2008; Barrett, 2000; Crickmore, Jones, & Engelke, & Mott, 2002; Engelke et al., 2009; Gordon et al., 2007; Levy et al., 2006; Moricca et al., 2012; Petitgout et al., 2012; Presler, 1998; Taras et al., 2004; Taylor et al., 2012). Thus, the findings of this review reflect current trends in role definition for nurses performing case management services. As such, major themes and ideas for increased understanding of care coordination and school nurses were described rather than specific interventions tied to outcomes.

Where a high-quality research base is non-existent or insufficient, The University of Colorado Hospital's model for evidence-based practice (Figure 2) offers options for application of the best available evidence (Goode & Piedalue, 1999). At the core of this model are the patient and the most current, valid research. Projecting from the core are nine points representing additional evidence sources. The nine points are, cost effective analysis, pathophysiology, retrospective or concurrent chart review, quality improvement and risk data, international, national and local standards, infection control data, patient preferences, clinical expertise, and benchmarking data. This model allows clinicians to appreciate each source of information as providing a worthwhile piece of the puzzle for influencing decision making and determining best-practice processes (Goode & Piedalue, 1999). This review adds important information to help define the scope of case

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management services in pediatric settings and provides limited examples of outcome measurements used in case management.

Discussion

Despite the significant differences in sample, setting, study design, and variables, most evidence sources revealed that there are core attributes, competencies, and functions common to nurse case managers across varied pediatric settings. When the elements and core concepts of case management by school nurse are compared to those of nurses in various medical, non-educational settings, notable areas of variation emerge.

Studies examining case management exclusively for students with asthma comprised the majority of specific sources of evidence related to school nurse role. This evidence could be considered a prototype description of the case management role for school nurses. Findings indicate that school nurses are limited, targeted, and specific in their activities. Moricca and colleagues (2012) describe case management activities as consisting of screening for risk of asthma, ensuring follow-up for care, and in-school management (e.g., asthma action plan, medication access). Similarly, Taras et al. (2004) explain that identification of students with asthma, making home visits, providing asthma education, and calling parents and doctors comprise case management activities. Nurses in Levy et al.'s study (2006) facilitated disease management and actions to decrease environmental triggers at school and home by communicating with students, parents, providers, and school personnel, in addition to delivering asthma education via a set curriculum, and weekly disease monitoring including follow-up after illnesses.

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Students in the asthma specific case management studies had positive health outcomes including improvement in quality of life, decrease in asthma symptoms, decreased utilization of urgent care and emergency department visits, increases in knowledge of disease management, increased availability of medication at school, increased peak flow meter use at school, and decreased school absences (Engelke et al., 2008; Levy et al., 2006; Moricca et al., 2012; Taras et al., 2004). Despite these achievements, the narrow concentration on prescribed actions for students with a single chronic illness suggests that further research is needed related to other experiences with case management. With the evidence that currently exists, generalizability to students with other chronic conditions, comorbidities, or higher levels of medical complexity in the school setting is limited. A substantial lack of evidence exists regarding provision of comprehensive case management by school nurses, which contributes to the vagueness, lack of understanding, development, and support for the role. Without an understanding of the importance of the services provided by school nurses, educational administrators will continue to underfund and understaff school health programs.

Having adequate time, staffing, training, administrative support, and fiscal resources to accomplish tasks and duties related to case management are key to creating effective systems of care (Betz & Redcay, 2005; Bonaiuto, 2007; Brustrom et al., 2012; Engelke et al., 2009; Moricca et al., 2012; Taras et al., 2004). Staffing levels are directly linked to funding sources and allocation of resources. Because case management is a complex and time-consuming activity, many authors argue that in order to provide

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quality care those services should not merely be incorporated into daily activities.

Adequate dedicated time and personnel need to be set aside to provide quality case management services (Betz & Redcay, 2005; Lindeke et al., 2002; Moricca et al., 2012).

The ANA advocates incorporation of interdisciplinary, team-based, care coordination experiences into the educational experience for all registered nurses (ANA, 2012). Advanced training in program formation, implementation, management, and evaluation along with development of leadership, education, advocacy, counseling, and research skills are necessary for nurses filling case management and care coordination roles (Betz & Redcay, 2004; Looman et al., 2013), including school nurses.

Interdisciplinary care coordination is difficult in the school setting because, in contrast to nurses in clinic or hospital settings, school nurses have limited access to medical records, providers, and sometimes parents.

The lack of adequate funding and reimbursement models or monetary incentives for providing care coordination is a major inhibiting factor for physicians, APRNs, and school nurses (Antonelli & Antonelli, 2004; Antonelli et al., 2008; Betz & Redcay, 2005; Gordon et al., 2007; Lindeke et al., 2002; Petitgout et al., 2012). Investment in an infrastructure that provides adequate reimbursement for non-physician-delivered care coordination, reimbursement for non-face-to-face activities, and for care coordination provided outside of the medical home setting, is imperative to maintain high quality programs (Antonelli et al., 2009; Gordon et al., 2007; Lindeke et al., 2002). Schools are required to assure equal student access to educational programs. For some students, case

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management is an absolute necessity and the services provided by the school nurse assure that access. School districts should have the ability to acquire public healthcare dollars for providing these services. Changes in funding may require legislative changes at state or national levels.

In order to understand which activities provide the best outcomes for students, measurement processes and adequate documentation must be established. Measuring and evaluating interventions and outcomes will allow nurses, administrators, and policy makers to better understand the effectiveness of case management and care coordination services. For school nurses, documentation of the broader measures of attendance and academic achievement, in addition to specific health outcomes, must be included. Use or adaptations of established tools, such as the ANA Framework for Measuring Nurse Contributions to Care Coordination or the AHRQ Care Coordination Measures Atlas are viable options (Kurtzman et al., 2013; McDonald et al., 2010). Establishment of a connection between case management provided by the school nurse and positive academic, health, and health system outcomes, will aid in reinforcing the value of the school nurse.

Strengths and Limitations

This integrative literature review provides an overview and appraisal of knowledge related to the role of school nurses in providing case management and care coordination services. Its strength is the fidelity to the methodological principles of the integrative review. Despite this, generalizations from the findings should be considered

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in light of the limitations presented by not only the evidence included but also the approach to synthesis. The major limitation for these findings is the low level of evidence. Because integrative reviews combine data from diverse methodologies, there is opportunity for inaccuracies and bias as conclusions are formulated. Notwithstanding, the findings suggest that nurses providing case management and care coordination share core role components that can be used as to conceptualize future research examining outcomes related to specific interventions provided by school nurses.

Conclusions and Implications for School Nursing Practice

Using Whittemore and Knafl's method, this integrative review explored and summarized the current literature related to the role of school nurses in providing case management and care coordination services. The following summary and key recommendations are developed from the evidence.

- There are core attributes, competencies, and functions common to case managers in varied pediatric settings, including schools.
- Nurses are in a key position to provide care coordination in varied pediatric settings and in the schools.
- Communication and collaboration between primary care providers, specialist providers, families, and agencies are essential in effective care coordination.
- Case management and care coordination provided by nurses has the potential to increase efficiency, and minimize gaps and redundancies, in patient care.

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- Having dedicated personnel, time, administrative support, and resources are important factors in implementing effective care coordination in any setting.
- Case management activities, and specialty-specific outcomes, must be evaluated and measured in order to demonstrate their effectiveness in promoting student health.
- Funding and reimbursement models for school nurses providing care coordination are necessary.

Many school nurses are already providing case management and care coordination services and integrating these key attributes, competencies, and functions. The evidence from this integrative review pinpoints areas for strengthening the role of school nurses in providing case management and care coordination in the educational setting. School nurses and nurse researchers must actively contribute to this body of knowledge by establishing effectiveness measures that take into account educational, medical, and health system-related outcomes. Developing and improving the tools used to document and measure those outcomes, and establishing baseline data from which to explain changes are crucial (Bonaiuto, 2007; Engelke et al., 2009; Weismuller et al., 2007). These data can then be used to demonstrate the effectiveness of case management in improving student health, attendance, and academic achievement. This evidence may drive increased monetary and resource support for school nurses and their care coordination role with students.

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Table 1

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication from 1990 – 2013	Publications prior to 1990
Peer-reviewed, gray literature (i.e. unpublished articles, dissertations, frameworks, policy documents, etc.)	
Nurse performed CM or CC, any setting	Case management services provided by non-nurses
US journals in English	Foreign journals

Note. CC = Care Coordination; CM = Case Management; US = United States.

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Table 2

Nurse Care Coordination in the Educational Setting

Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management; Goals	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of CM program utilizing nursing students in the educational setting (Barrett, 2000)	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tertiary prevention • Community-based actions • Interdisciplinary team leader • Identification of students at high risk • Health assessment • Health care planning • Coordination of services • Monitoring outcomes 	<p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insight gained by nursing students from participation in CM • Intensive involvement and home visits by nursing students offered in-depth understanding of issues and concerns • Anecdotal comments of benefit to parents
Description of a CM program in the educational setting (Bonaiuto, 2007)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CM follows “expanded nursing process” • Resource needs and availability established • Collaborative partners engaged • Students regularly monitored • SN served as an advocate for all parties • SN worked with Coordinated School Health Team 	<p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized practice • Policy and procedures • Identify outcomes • Establish data collection procedures • Develop forms • Educate support staff • Demonstrate effectiveness of SN CM to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduce health related barriers to learning ○ Increase benefit of educational program
Description of CM program in the educational setting for children with asthma, diabetes, severe	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build long-term relationships • Focus on prevention • Interventions individualized (including: teaching, counseling, direct care, working with teachers, school personnel, and families, making referrals) 	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved QOL for students with asthma ($p = .001$) • Symptoms of asthma decreased ($p = .001$) • Overall improvement in care for students with

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management; Goals	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
allergies, seizures, sickle-cell anemia (Engelke et al., 2008)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Goals individualized 	diabetes ($p = .01$) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Barriers to care for students with diabetes decreased ($p = .075$)
Description of CM program in the educational setting (Engelke et al., 2009)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment – academic history, health record, physical and psychosocial, parents, teachers Interventions – direct care, education and counseling, teacher and staff education, family education and support, CM Goals (individualized) – safe school environment, symptom and self-care management, academic success, supportive family and peers, CM 	Conclusions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to collect baseline data and measure outcomes Decrease fragmentation and duplication Enhance quality Cost-effective clinical outcomes Individual academic improvement and optimal health
Description of an asthma CM program in an urban school district (Levy et., 2006)	II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education Regular monitoring of student health status Coordination of care between students and families and school personnel and providers to facilitate management of disease 	Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decrease school absences: CM schools average of 4.38 days absent, UC schools 8.18 days (~ 3.8 more days attended by CM students) Decrease hospital utilization: CM had fewer urgent care/ED visits ($p < .001$ for each semester and $p < .0001$ over entire year) Increase student knowledge and skills related to asthma management: CM group

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management; Goals	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of a CM program for students with asthma in the educational setting (Moricca et al., 2012)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screening for asthma risk • Ensuring appropriate medical follow-up • In-school management of disease process (asthma action plan and medications at school) 	<p>($p < .0001$), UC group not surveyed.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced illness absence • Early identification and treatment <p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CM requires additional SN time • Need to measure/track CM activities
Description of a SN CM program for students with asthma (Taras et al., 2004)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of students with asthma • Home visits • Chronic condition (asthma) education • Calls to parents • Calls to MD 	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased availability of medications at school • Increased peak flow meter use at school • Change in asthma severity • Asthma tracking with CM improved overall medical management of asthma <p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At recommended nurse to student ratio can be incorporated into typical duties
Description of CM program for children with asthma in home and school (Van Roeyen, 2013)	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and track students with asthma • Assure access to medications • Individualized asthma action plan for students • Encourage participation in school-related activities (physical activities) • Standard protocol • Educate school personnel and students 	<p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective control of asthma at home and at school depends on SN provided asthma education for children, families, caregivers • Identification and elimination of triggers • Asthma management leads to improved

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management; Goals	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and reduce triggers • Ensure communication or collaboration among personnel, families, health professionals • Discussion of asthma-related policies 	<p>school performance and general well-being</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SN knowledge of laws related to asthma care in schools • Use of action plan decreases exacerbations in school

Note. CC = Care Coordination; CM = Case Management; ED = Emergency Department; MD = Medical Doctor; SN = School Nurse; QOL = Quality of Life; UC = Usual Care.

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Table 3

Nurse Care Coordination Outside of the Educational Setting

Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of CC program in a community-based, general pediatric practice (Antonelli & Antonelli, 2004)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phone or other contact with entity or group associated with the patient (i.e. parent, school, hospital, home health agency, etc.) • Contact with consulting specialist (telephone, in-person, written) • Contact with primary care • Written report to an agency • Chart review • Patient-focused research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not all aspects of CC need to be performed or guided by MD • Tool for measure of services provided is useful <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Decrease in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Referrals for office visits ○ ED care ○ Hospital admissions ○ Subspecialist referrals ○ Lab or x-ray utilization <p>Increase in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Referrals to community agencies
Description of activities, costs, outcomes of focused CC in pediatric primary care setting (Antonelli et al., 2008).	VI	<p>Focus of encounters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical and medical management • Referral management • Social services (housing, food, clothing, etc.) • Education and school • Developmental and behavioral • Mental health • Growth and nutrition • Legal and judicial <p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telephone • Confer with PCP • Chart review 	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of CC per encounter, depending on staff providing care = \$4.39 to \$12.86. Mean = \$7.78. • Physician CC was highest cost, RN CC lower cost and higher incidents of helping avoid use of high cost health care services • Tool for measure of services provided found useful <p>Outcomes:</p>

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process forms • Email • Meeting or case conference • Letters or reports • Patient research or care planning 	Decrease in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pediatrician office or clinic visits ○ ED and Subspecialist visits ○ Hospitalizations ○ Lab use ○ Specialized therapy Increase in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Referrals ○ Met family needs ○ Obtained MD orders ○ Advise home management ○ Family advocacy ○ Labs reviewed
Description of framework for CC in pediatric health care system (Antonelli et al., 2009)	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactive, planned, comprehensive • Promotes self-care skills and independence • Emphasizes cross-organizational relationships • Development of partnerships and team-building (family-centered, culturally effective) • Proficient management of communication • Assessments (team-based, family-centered, strengths noted) • Proper care planning • Integrates resources and knowledge • Goal/outcome oriented • Adaptable and flexible • Continuous learning • Technology utilized 	Recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance and outcome measures • Strategies for workforce development and education • Policy support, and financing • Comprehensive services including family input Conclusions, CC can: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance clinical and functional outcomes • Increase patient and family satisfaction • Reduce costs while increasing efficiency and effectiveness
Description of	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical Expert (develop 	Recommendations:

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
role of nurse care coordinator as sub-specialty transition services from pediatric to adult settings (Betz & Redcay, 2005)		<p>standard of care from evidence, care planning, family and youth-centered involving adolescent in decision making, facilitates referrals, coordinate support services, creates interagency partnerships)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultant (comprehensive consultation on transition planning) • Change Agent (develops service models and training programs, transition resources, support programs) • Leader (provide direction and ensure principles based on best-practice and evidence, initiate partnerships, promote interagency planning: IEPs, 504 plan, etc.) • Researcher (develop, implement, evaluate evidence-based programs, collaborate in studies) • Educator (educates colleagues, families, develops resources) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family and youth-centered • Includes health education and employment and community living needs • Care coordinator is specialized role in transition services separate from other • Needs dedicated time and fiscal resources
Description of CC program in Spina Bifida specialty clinics (Brustrom et al., 2012)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment (medical, transportation and housing, family issues and conflicts, financial needs, factors hindering functioning) • Coordination of care across providers (scheduling appointments with multiple internal and external 	<p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet overall needs of child and family • Coordinate multiple services during one clinic visit • Help children become independent, reach maximum potential

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of CC by APRN in tertiary care hospital-based program (Cady et al.,	VI	<p>providers, coordinating clinic visit logistics, coordinate with community agencies, SNs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication (with in-clinic and outside of clinic staff, providers, colleagues, with family in providing education, as point-person for family resource from home) • Link to resources (providing referrals or information to resources) • Follow-up (determine if services were received and utilized, confirmation of attendance at appointments or receipt of needed tests or labs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute and chronic condition management • Coordination with providers • Coordination with community resources • Parental follow-up, 	<p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate staffing and staff support needed • Clinic day logistics coordinated, manage length of day, adequate time with each provider, adequate physical space • Disease specific resource issues • Intra-team communication responsibilities, who communicates what and to whom • Understand patient and family dynamics that affect understanding, follow-through, transportation • Funding (lack of adequate funding) • Communication between providers and families sometimes lacks openness and detail <p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate staffing • Flexibility with clinic appointments • Families linked to resources <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison of difference in number of episodes across 3 year period showed increase between years 1 and 2 (<i>p</i>

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
2013)		education, support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appointment scheduling • Inpatient communication and discharge planning 	< .001) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parents felt it important: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To have one place to call ○ Assistance in managing child's complex condition ○ Organized and accessible medical information ○ Someone to clarify orders for other providers • APRN benefits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Skilled at recognition of acute and chronic health conditions and potential for poor outcomes ○ Knows importance of teaching parents how to monitor and manage care ○ Dedicated person for information and management
Description of community-based asthma CM program (Crickmore et al., 2002)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of children with asthma • Documentation of peak flow rates • Ongoing education • Provision of follow up care • Care provided over the continuum – school, home, hospital, ED, MD office • Levels of CM individualized to needs of child and family 	Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant improvement in peak flow readings • Significant reduction in inpatient admissions Recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent medical management of asthma • Education for patients and families about the prevention and care of asthma

SCHOOL NURSE CARE COORDINATION INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of a CC model in tertiary-primary care setting with medically complex, fragile children (Gordon et al., 2007)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single point of contact for families, PCPs, community • Familiarity with child's condition • Care planning • Facilitate communication among specialists and PCPs • Attend specialist and PCP appointments with family • Work with outside agencies – durable medical equipment, insurers • Home visits • Attend school meetings • Psychosocial support • CC education for parents and caregiver 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate use of the hospital, ED, community resources • Reduction in school absenteeism • Address financial concerns limiting access to care • Reduction of factors contributing to asthma symptoms <hr/> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in days hospitalized ($p < .001$) • Reduction in clinic visits ($p < .001$) • Reduction in short-stay visits ($p < .001$) • Reduction in hospital payments due to shift to outpatient clinic care ($p < .001$) • Anecdotal comments of family satisfaction having single point of contact <p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrollment criteria should be specific • CC by MD better reimbursement rate
Description of a CC model for children with special needs (Kaufman & Blanchon,	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multidisciplinary approach • Identification of medical condition • Individualized, comprehensive treatment plan • Monitoring outcome results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus of this model was meeting child's special needs within a broad system of specialty and primary services while using prior authorization for cost containment

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
1996)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of treatment plan as needed • Enhancing communication • Improving delivery of service to promote quality and cost-effectiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of families' needs and family involvement required for best care
Description of care management program for medically fragile children (Lewis et al., 1992)	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the patient and family needs for resources and support • Development and selection of suitable resources and support to promote or sustain health status goals • Monitoring of patient health and medical regimens • Collaboration with other providers in the health-care system on behalf of patients and families • Communication • Advocacy • Teaching care management skills to families 	<p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognize the specialized needs and strengths of the child and family unit • Facilitate the support of the child's optimal physical function, growth, and development in the most appropriate family and community setting • Promote optimal family function to respond to the child care demands • Empower family to direct and manage care of their own child to the greatest extent possible • Transition to the community-based care management option for utilizing local care manager in educational system
Description of family-centered CC program for children with special needs across	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family-centered – family constant in child's life • Facilitate collaboration in all aspects of care planning • Respect racial, ethnic, cultural, socioeconomic diversity 	<p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate suitable access to services • Promote continuity of care • Enhance child and family wellbeing

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
multiple settings (Lindeke et al., 2002)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand family strengths, individuality and coping methods • Share all information with family • Encourage and facilitate family connections • Integrate developmental needs of children and families • Implement policies and programs to help with emotional and financial needs • Help create health care system that is accessible, flexible, culturally competent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balance between cost-containment and quality of care • Educate and train others about the function and process of CC • Increase communication between systems providing CC • Create systems allowing for extensive time and effort required for CC • Create systems of reimbursement for CC
Description of value of APRN in providing CC (Looman et al., 2013)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate access to providers and resources • Single point of contact, advocate, information resource • Education and anticipatory guidance • Interventions addressing family needs • Care planning • Leader in coordination of multidisciplinary systems • Initiate and manage referrals, monitor for overlap or gaps in service • Prepare for and facilitate transitions • Assessment, management and evaluation of acute and chronic conditions • Write prescriptions 	<p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the provision of health promotion and chronic condition care • Ensure ongoing, proactive, and planned care activities • Use effective communication strategies • Develop, improve, measure, monitor, and sustain quality outcomes – clinical, functional, satisfaction, cost <p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build relationships among family and team • Support primary caregiving role of family • Assess child and family

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of a hospital-based CC program (Petitgout et al., 2012)	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist with scheduling • Promote self-care skills and independence • Link to resources – financial, community support, homecare • Manage care services – organize and direct services, facilitate communication, advocate for the child and family (avoid duplication of services, unnecessary costs) • Discharge services – teaching, medications and therapies, equipment, nursing care, school and work integration • Follow-up services – ongoing evaluation of nursing care needs, phone triage, manage re-admissions • Development of proactive plan of care with input from patient/family and involved professionals (improving QOL of child and family) • Facilitate communication between multiple professionals • Optimizing health – physical 	<p>needs and assets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate primary care and subspecialty co-management • Foster cultural competence • Develop leadership, advocacy, communication, education, counseling, and research skills <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In a convenience sample of children having a tracheostomy, children in CC program had a mean LOS of 33.95 days (SD, 23.89) while those without CC had a mean LOS of 49.59 days (SD 44.09) (p = .10) • Estimation of \$3 million savings in hospital costs with CC program • Caregiver satisfaction rating of the overall CC program of “very good” <p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification and evaluation of quality indicators • Use of PNP staff to enhance access to services • Development of funding sources not restricted to MD provided care only

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
Description of CC model for children with special health care needs at a Shriner's Hospital (Presler, 1998)	VII	<p>and emotional</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of child and family needs, concerns and priorities • Coordinating all facets of multidisciplinary team • Integration of inpatient and outpatient services • Promotion of optimum health and functional outcomes across developmental continuum • Care must be accessible • Advocacy-focused to help navigate the maze of health and social services • Community based identification of resources, preparing child and family for meaningful participation in the community, transitions from school to work, enhancing community infrastructure • Comprehensive to include primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of health care • Coordinated for expedient referral processes, ongoing communication and collaboration, plan of care for within and across agencies • Cost-effective promoting effectiveness and efficiency • Culturally responsive care that respects languages, beliefs, and values 	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration project of model found of patient and family survey respondents: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 66% felt increased satisfaction ○ 49% found it easier to get equipment • Shriner's Hospital demonstration project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 48% reported better understanding of services and resources ○ 45% believed people cared about their child ○ 43% reported fewer trips to provider office ○ 41% worried less about their child ○ 36% reported better functioning for the child ○ 35% reported increase in community-based therapies ○ 29% reported fewer complications ○ 22% fewer hospitalizations ○ 38% of staff respondents felt increased job satisfaction <p>Recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitation of appropriate access to services and resources

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developmentally appropriate supporting child's highest potential • Family-centered care that sees family as constant for child and ultimate decision making • Individualized and specific to the needs of the child • Outcome-focused for short-term and long-term goals • Proactive focus on prevention of secondary disabilities and early intervention • Standards based with nationally recognized guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of care continuity through all areas of the system • Provision of support enhancing family well-being • Improvement outcomes in health, development, education, vocation, psychosocial, and functional aspects of life • Maximization of efficient and effective use of health care resources
Description of nursing CM of the chronically ill child (Smith, 1994)	VII	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal oriented activities that help organize, coordinate, monitor care delivery. • Based on measurable objectives created to meet the needs of the child and family • Provision of care along a continuum decreasing fragmentation across settings • Process more than a structure or outcome • Process is four steps that progress and returns to each step as needed • Assessment, planning, intervention, evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early identification and intervention • Continuity of care through episodes of illness • Improve parental advocacy skills • Increase social and developmental skills for children • Professional growth and interdisciplinary collegiality for nurses
Description of CC for children with special	VI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient and family levels of comfort in navigating health care system is assessed • Family is coached in 	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Families receiving CC from care counselor felt child received well-

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Focus of Article, Author/year	Level of Evidence	Elements and Core Concepts of Case Management	Outcomes, Conclusions, and Recommendations
healthcare needs (Taylor et al., 2012)		developing coordination of skills, including partnering with providers, tracking and organizing clinical information and identify community supports <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of complexity of care needed – number and variety of services required • Collaboration with the family care team to define needs and ensures clarity in care plan • Coordinated, centralized scheduling for patients to ensure continuity during transitions in care • Long-term single point person to oversee care plan 	coordinated care, had someone to help coordinate care, and had access to resources and staff compared to families receiving UC ($p < .0001$) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support in building core competencies in CC and advocacy provided for families • Care binder tool, complex scheduling management, community resource database, used to assist families

Note. APRN = Advanced Practice Registered Nurse; CC = Care Coordination; DCF = Department of Children and Families; ED = Emergency Department; IEP = Individualized Education Plan; LOS = Length of Stay; PCP = Primary Care Provider; PNP = Pediatric Nurse Practitioner; QOL = Quality of Life; RN = Registered Nurse; SD = Standard Deviation; SN = School Nurse; UC = Usual Care.

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Figure 1. Flowchart of search and screening process. Adapted from “Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement,” by Moher et al., 2009, *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 151, p. 267. Copyright 2009 by PRISMA Group. Adapted with permission.

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Figure 2. University of Colorado Hospital’s Evidence-based multidisciplinary practice model. Reprinted from “Evidence-based clinical practice,” C. Goode & F. Piedalue, 1999, *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 29, p. 15-21. Copyright 1999 by University of Colorado Hospital. Reprinted with permission.

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APPENDIX B

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR THE *JOURNAL OF SCHOOL NURSING*, 2014

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THE JOURNAL OF SCHOOL NURSING**Manuscript Submission Guidelines**

The Journal of School Nursing (JOSN) is the official journal of the National Association of School Nurses. It is a peer-reviewed journal whose purpose is to provide a forum for advancing the specialty of school nursing, contributing to knowledge development about school nursing practice, and promoting the professional growth of school nurses thus ultimately advancing the health of school children. See the [Aims and Scope](#) link for a description of types of manuscripts sought. Manuscripts from all disciplines related to child, school, and community health are welcome.

Because JOSN seeks manuscripts that bring new perspectives and innovations to school nursing, we urge authors to review previously published articles related to their topic in order to (1) build on the comprehensive body of published literature on the subject and (2) ensure the uniqueness of their own article's contribution.

Average time from submission to first decision: 27 days

Types of Articles

For all types of manuscripts, please see *The Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association, Sixth Edition (2010)* for guidance in developing the abstract. Identify three to 10 keywords or short phrases placed below the abstract. These keywords will be published with the abstract. It is important to embed keywords in the abstract. Keywords from Index Medicus are helpful.

Original Research Reports

Original research reports can address specific clinical problems that affect individuals in the school community or the school population. For intervention studies and randomized controlled trials, please review the [Consort Statement](#) including a description of the Flow Diagram for inclusion in the manuscript. Original research reports include pilot, preliminary, and feasibility studies as well as studies of all designs including epidemiological, quantitative and qualitative studies, and clinical trials. The implications for school nursing and school health services delivery should be identified. See the *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association, Sixth Edition (2010)* for guidance in formulating elements of a research report as well as the reference list and tables. The following criteria guide the peer reviews of original research manuscripts:

1. The title and abstract are descriptive of the study.
2. The purpose of the study is clearly stated.
3. Research questions or hypotheses are clear.
4. The significance of the study is clear and builds on previous research.
5. The literature review is adequate, current (most within the last five to ten years), and synthesized as well as related to the purpose of the paper.
6. Theoretical/conceptual framework
 1. Described/operationalized
 2. Guides the research
7. The purpose, theoretical framework, design, and methods are congruent.
8. Methods include:

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1. Design
2. Population/setting
3. Sampling procedure description, sample size rationale
4. Measures described
5. The data collection and analysis procedures are accurate, appropriate, and clearly reported.
6. The statistics are described in an understandable manner.
7. Human subjects' protection is assured and ethics maintained.
9. Discussion synthesizes the results.
10. The application to school nursing practice is relevant, clear, and practical.
11. Limitations and recommendations for future research are presented.

Literature Reviews

Literature reviews should provide a comprehensive review of the literature and synthesize findings related to specific problems or school health programs. Simple or narrative reviews of the literature as well as rapid assessments, integrated reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analysis or qualitative reviews are acceptable. All reviews should be guided by a clear statement of purpose or research question. Search procedures should be reported, including search terms as well as inclusion and exclusion criteria. All reviews require a synthesis of the findings. While the following links are useful resources for systematic and meta-analysis literature reviews, they can also provide structural information for all reviews: the [Cochrane Collaboration](#); [Joanna Briggs Institute](#); [PRISMA Group](#). School nursing and school health services implications drawn from the reviews strengthen the relevance for *The JOSN*. The following criteria guide the peer review of Literature Review manuscripts:

1. The title and abstract are descriptive of the review.
2. The purpose of the review is clearly stated.
3. Research questions articulated.
4. Databases searched are described.
5. The sampling procedure is clearly described, including inclusion/exclusion criteria and time span of published articles.
6. The data collection and analysis procedures of literature are accurate, appropriate, and clearly reported.
7. For meta-analyses, statistics are described in an understandable manner.
8. The results are clear and address the purpose or answer the research question(s).
9. Results of the review show synthesis of manuscripts reviewed.
10. The application to school nursing practice is relevant, clear, and practical.

Evidence Based Practice or Policy Reports

Evidence based practice reports of change projects or resulting policies and projects assessing program quality should include an introduction reporting a clear statement of the issue and purpose of the project. The introduction should also include a synthesis of the evidence base guiding the program or policy. The methods section should include ethical considerations and setting description. A description of the measures and the implementation should be included as well as the analysis used in evaluation. Results can include outcomes, guidelines derived for the program as well as lessons learned. Implications for school nursing and school health services are expected. The [Squire Standards for Quality Improvement Reporting Excellence](#) provides guidelines for quality improvement project manuscripts. The following criteria guide the peer review of Evidence Based Practice or Policy Report manuscripts.

1. The title and abstract are descriptive of the study.
2. The issue/problem statement or rationale for policy change and purpose are clearly stated.
3. The evidence base is adequate, current (most within the last five to ten years) and well synthesized.
4. The purpose and methods are congruent.
5. Methods include:
 1. Description of the setting and population related to the project or policy change.
 2. The data collection and evaluation procedures are accurate, appropriate and clearly reported.
 3. The measures assessing the change project are clearly described. The data collection and evaluation procedures are accurate, appropriate, and clearly reported.
 4. Project implementation/policy development steps are well described.
 5. Statistics and/or analysis procedures are described in an understandable manner.
 6. Human subjects' protection is described.
6. The results are clear and address the purpose statement. Use of tables as appropriate.
7. Discussion synthesizes the results and identifies lessons learned.
8. The application to school nursing practice is relevant, clear, and practical.

Commentaries

Commentaries are shorter manuscripts (no more than 5-10 pages including references) addressing emerging issues in school health or previous publications in *The JOSN*. Commentaries are scholarly manuscripts that include references and call attention to issues for school nursing and the school health community. The following criteria guide the peer review of Commentaries:

1. The title and abstract are descriptive of the commentary.
2. The purpose of the commentary is clearly stated.
3. The supporting literature is adequate and current (most within the last five to ten years).
4. The critique or comment regarding the current issue or previous published manuscript in *The JOSN* is clear and not personal.
5. The commentary narrative is congruent with the purpose.
6. The narrative is scholarly, properly supported, and clearly stated.
7. Human subjects' protection is assured and ethics maintained.

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8. The application to school nursing practice is relevant, clear, and practical.
9. Commentary does not exceed 10 pages including references.

Letters to the Editor

Letters to the Editor provide a forum for commenting on articles published in *The JOSN* and topics of general interest in school health care. The length should not exceed 800 words of text with a minimal number of references. One table or figure may be included, if necessary. Any comments regarding a specific article must include the title, author(s), and date of publication. Letters that contain questions or critique of a previously published paper will be forwarded to the author(s) of that article for a reply. The sharing of ideas, experiences, opinions, and alternative views is encouraged. The Executive Editor of *The JOSN* reserves the right to accept, reject, or excerpt letters for clarity and appropriateness of content, and to accommodate space requirements. Submit Letters to the Editor to <http://mc.manuscriptcentral.com/josn>. The following criteria guide the review Letters to the Editor.

1. The title is descriptive of the letter to the editor.
2. The purpose of the letter is clearly stated.
3. The supporting literature is adequate and current (most within the last five to ten years).
4. The narrative regarding the current issue or previous published manuscript in *The JOSN* is clear and not personal.
5. The narrative is congruent with the purpose.
6. The narrative is relevant, clear, and practical.
7. The letter narrative does not exceed 800 words including references.

Referenced Editorials

Editorials are written by the editor, the editorial board, or invited authors. Editorials address current issues important to the health of school children and school nursing practice. The purpose of editorials is to stimulate scholarly thought among school nurses and other school health practitioners and researchers.

Manuscript Format:

Manuscripts should be prepared in accordance with the guidelines set forth in the *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association*, 6th edition. Manuscripts, including abstracts (150 words) and references, should be double-spaced, using 12-point Times New Roman font, left justified margins, and one-inch margins on all sides. No identifying information about the author(s) should be in the body of the paper, abstract, or figures. Manuscripts should not exceed 20 pages, excluding abstract, references, tables, and figures. Tables should be typed one to a page with any notes/legends typed on the same page. Label each figure with its number and legend. All tables, figures, graphs, and drawings should follow the reference list and not placed in the body of the manuscript.

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Manuscripts should be submitted electronically at <http://mc.manuscriptcentral.com/josn>. Authors will be required to set up an online account on the SAGETRACK system, powered by ScholarOne.

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Email questions to the Editor.

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APPENDIX C

FIGURE AND MODEL USE APPROVAL

Oman, Kathy - UCH <Kathy.Oman@uchealth.org>
To: Rachel McDanahan <mcdanr@csu.fullerton.edu>

Tue, Mar 4, 2014 at 9:11 AM

Rachel, you have our permission to use the model as long as you cite the reference. If you proceed to publish your capstone project and want to use the Colorado model, you will need formal permission for the journal you submit to. We can provide that if needed. Kathy

Please note my new email address

Kathy Oman, PhD, RN, FAEN, FAAN

Research Nurse Scientist/CNS

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